

***MGNREGS as a Tool of Financial Security among People During
Pandemic Covid19: Study in Peringamala Grama Panchayath***

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INTRODUCTION

Mahatma Gandhi national rural employment guaranty scheme was launched in India in 2005 as a vision to poverty eradication. It provides 100 working days of unskilled labor on public project works. The scheme was passed in order to reduce the condition of unemployment by providing job for each adult. It was set up ambitiously for decline the rate of poverty in rural area which was unbalanced with the urban sector. Then the mahatma Gandhi national rural employment guaranty act was passed in 2005. India, where a large number of farmers suicide by leaving their family in debt and a state of helpless condition, the act was a hope to change the situation. It was not constructed in sudden process. It was done in a decentralization process in which specialists from grass root level are participated.

The idea was first generated in last decade of twenty first century by proposing a pilot scheme to provide rural employment for farmers. From the time of implementation, it has changed as an alternative income generation for farmers in lean season. In infrastructure development in rural areas, MGNREGS has been a better tool of local self-government. They are worked mainly in water resources rejuvenation, it's construction, rejuvenation works in fields, etc. Through NREGS workers the cultivation is enhanced also the food security. The scheme is mainly targeting the unemployed poor. Above 90% of workers are women and most of them have age above 40. So, the scheme has helped the women to empower. A situation of income generation islot for generate empower for a woman. Many women who were only assigned to do the kitchen works got an opportunity for income generation. It is not a little thing for an Indian woman to earn an average of twenty thousand rupees annually.

The scheme was passed in those times when the rate of internal migration was in a

higher state. The implementation of scheme aimed to push back the population from migration, whether it is from rural to urban or in between two states. It succeeds in making job among rural population but couldn't reduce the rate of migration. As mentioned earlier it differentiate itself from earlier schemes in its grassroots level approach. The legal provisions are there if the work is delayed or denied. It is funded by the central government and 75% of cost of material for works. The central and state governments audit the works and reports separately by the central and state employment guaranty council.

The work is carried out in grama panchayath level and panchayath have significant power in managing the works. Grama panchayath decides about the work and they can reject or accept the recommendations. The employment rate has increased by 240% in the last 10 years and it helped to reduce the exploitation of labor, wage discrimination and so gender gap. The gramasabha prioritize the work and the primary audit is also conducted.

Covid-19 and workers in India

On 11 march 2020 covid 19 was declared as a pandemic in India. Following that a country wide lockdown was happened in 24th march. Initiatives was first did in order to reduce the no number of active cases and also prevent the chances of spreading. But despite of all the initiatives India currently counts the active number of cases to about 3 crores. By experts, the best way to avoid the chances of spreading is to regularly wash hands, use mask, maintain social distance and remain homes when it became necessary. The country went to lock down for 4 months and remained partially for eight months. It was the time when the country asked it's each and every population for contribute to their country. It was the time for doing social responsibility and solidarity. The economy of our country is rolling in markets. One of the main components in rolling the money is the labor sector. So, they have a great role in our economy. But the covid condition has trapped them in an unprecedented crisis. The lockdown shuttered all the works for a period of three months. During that period, only the government employees were getting the uninterrupted income. The major population of our country is finding their earning through daily wages. That big population of daily earning was ended for that period. It was the responsibility of the state to stabilize the market economy in the absence of the daily earnings and also to help the huge population for their existence by economic reforms. The later duty of the state was not so easy and it required more competency which was not in action all over the country. If the mentioned one was exhibited even in an average way, the reports of deaths over migrated workers, suicide of small retailers were not in reality. It is the fact that some states like Kerala maintained living conditions of migrated workers and daily wage workers along with the native people by providing food kit and establishing community kitchens. It was a new idea for a condition like this. But despite of this, the challenges confronting India's working population have made them panic. They strive to accomplish their needs and most often failures are the results. The population is still facing difficulty in meeting their requirements. Because, after the lockdown the relief on the economic refunding has been abandoned. At the same time the pre lockdown condition of daily works has not been in action. i.e., the current status of the daily workers is unbalanced. During the time of lock down a large portion of visual media and reports were populated by the spectacles of vulnerability i.e., the pictures of migrated workers travelling thousands of kilometers along with their family languages on back. It is bitter to report about the death cases among them. As per PLFS report, India has about 470 million workers. Among them, 245 were self-employed, 107 each were casual and regular workers. This population have an average monthly income ranging in between 5000 and 10000. The sudden lockdown has brought them in a state of chaos and havoc and a population having no social security forced to withstand the challenges of the uncertainty in their life. As per the center of monitoring Indian economy about 120 million jobs were lost in first month of lockdown. Also, it was the time of harvest. Due to the lockdown the bringing of machineries and it's repair also hitin trouble. The standard workers action network (SWAN) reported just after the announcement

of lockdown that, 50% workers have ration only for one day and 72% have only for 2 days. Another study conducted by center of Indian trade union (CITU) 29% workers don't have rice. Almost 500 people had neither a ration card nor an Aadhaar card. Due to this they were not eligible for the ration of Delhi government.

MGNREGS as a tool of eliminating poverty and unemployment has very much importance in Indian labor system. It was also hit in covid. Rural development department has revealed about the decline number of person working days in rural areas. Like other daily works NREGS works were also stopped in the first days of lockdown. As mentioned earlier, it was a tool of unemployment in rural area, among most of the population it was only the income source. So many families get affected with the unemployment days which lasted for a period of 3 months. Not only about the Labor days, but also the social interaction among the people. In the period of three months the workers withstand the conditions with the help of government. Each government's implemented policies helped the workers to manage the days. Another face of workers were also existed which showed the inability of people to withstand the conditions and losses to the conditions. So, when the unlock was started the NREGS working days were needed so that, the people who lost their daily jobs were to be satisfied. Reports says that after lockdown the new applications are increased in number in comparing with last years. Actually, it has become the real tool of ensuring jobs to the population who lost jobs in lockdown. According to the data revealed by government, despite the threat of second wave in the last year, the demand for working days was in rise. So MGNREGS has become the safest place to ensure the job days.

PANDEMIC AND LABOUR SYTEM

The massive loss of jobs and incomes as a result of the pandemic and the lockdown has sparked widespread worry. What's more concerning is that the effects of these shocks are unlikely to have been evenly distributed across the workforce.

I suggest that the effects of the shocks would be particularly harsh on various types of workers, using data from the most recent Periodic Labour Force Survey (PLFS 2018-19), which reflects the state of the labour market prior to the Covid-19 crisis. These are the employees with less education who are often employed in low-paying, precarious, and unstable jobs in industries that have been struck the worst by the shocks. As a result, we can expect the crisis to exacerbate pre-existing inequalities in India's dualistic labour market, which has been marked by stark disparities between a small percentage of the workforce engaged in jobs that provide income stability and social security benefits on the one hand, and a disproportionately large proportion engaged in informal employment on the other.

Self-employed workers accounted for 52 percent of the workforce in 2018–19, the most recent year for which statistics is available. Over 95% of self-employed people were either own accountworkers (those who run businesses without using hired labour) or unpaid family workers.

Employers accounted for less than 5% of self-employed people. About a quarter of the workforce was employed as casual labourers, with no guaranteed salary or job security. They

were also beyond the scope of employer-employee ties that provided employment-related benefits, just like the self-employed. The remaining 24% of the workforce was made up of regular wage salaried (RWS) employees. These workers were paid on a regular basis rather than on the basis of a daily or periodic work contract renewal. They were better off than temporary workers as a result, but not everyone had access to social security benefits or long-term employment contracts.

Thousands of temporary labourers and self-employed people have returned to their hometowns in the aftermath of the Covid-19 epidemic in cities like Mumbai and Pune. Those who remain in cities face reduced working hours, layoffs, furloughs, and income decreases. This, however, is not unique to Maharashtra. According to the International Labour Organization (ILO), the number of workers in India who could be affected by the shutdown could reach 364 million or more, including those in casual work, self-employment, and regular occupations that aren't protected. According to an ILO document on the rapid assessment of the impact of the Covid-19 crisis on employment released last month, India had been experiencing slower economic growth and rising unemployment even before the Covid-19 crisis, problems that were dramatically exacerbated by the pandemic and the ensuing lockdown. Casual workers and self-employed people are most likely to lose their jobs and salaries, according to the documents. In India, almost three-quarters of the workforce is non-regular, either self-employed or casual.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Reethika khara (2011) in her book "The battle for employment guarantee" discusses about the battle for employment guarantees from the enactment of low to the fight against corruption and workers struggle to organized and defend their rights.

Katar singh in his book "Rural development principles, policies and management" describes about rural development and agriculture and its planning.

National sample survey organisation (2011) conducted a survey on "employment-unemployment in India at periodic intervals" to getting parameters of employment - unemployment characteristics at national and state level.

N P Abdul azees (2011) in his book "MGNREGS, provision, implementation and performance" discusses the various legal provisions of the act and its performance level in various states especially in Kerala. And how it impacted the life of women.

Saritha kausal in her book "Indian women: health, education and poverty" she focused on the real life of women and understands the plight of poor women around the world.

Supriya roy choudhary in her book "Old classes and new spaces: Urban poverty, unorganized labour and new unions" discusses the adverse impacts on unskilled labour in globalized era.

Choudhary describes that labour becomes vulnerable in the face of increasing competition and

Received: 22 July 2023

Revised: 2 August 2023

Final Accepted 8 August 2023

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8224098>

fast changing technology and foot loose capital is hard to tax. Thus diminishing the state's capacity to provide welfare.

C N Thresia in her book "Women workers in agriculture: Gender discrimination, working condition and health status" discusses gender discrimination working condition and health status of women workers in agriculture. It describes the socio-economic background of both women in agricultural and unorganized work and narrates nature of work and working conditions.

Jan breman (2001) in the book "An informed labour system, end of labour market dualism" described the consequences of market led mode of capitalist production. The author has observed the closure of textile mill in Ahmedabad and says that it is the consequence of liberalization.

Dibyentu miti and **kunal sen** in their book "The informal sector in India: A means of exploitation and accumulation" they shares two views about informal sector. One is a site for capital accumulation with paid workers having bad conditions. Another view is that, being aninformal sector, it should be an economic dynamism and entrepreneurial activity

Jayan Jose Thomas in his book "Labour and industrialization in Kerala" he describes about the organisation of labour and industrialization in Kerala. It look back to the worker organisation which improved the wage rate and working conditions. He has also argues that industrial backwardness of Kerala is due to the labour problem.

Kannan (2005) has stressed that the potential of NREGA could be more fully realized if human development had been more fully prioritized like child care facilities

Dreze and sen (1991) preventing dislocation of families in search of jobs and food

Institute of applied man power and research(2009) conducted a study and revealed that, low earning level of number of beneficiaries declined and the and the number of households reporting marginally high income has increased.

Sudha Narayan (2008) for applied man power and research, have examined the role ofMGNREGS among people of certain places in lean seasons.

NSSO 64th round survey(2009)reported that an average of 79 rupees was earning by both maleand female workers per day which was higher than the daily earning of casual workers.

MGNREGA Sameeksha (2012) narrated all about the working condition of people. It described about the role of NREGS as it helped Indian women to participate in development process. Apart from this, sameeksha includes it's working, funding, areas of research, etc.

The economic times (2021) reported that the covid crisis has pushed higher educated people of Karnataka state to enrol under MGNREGS. It includes graduates, post graduates and PhD holders. It brings the attention on the condition of unemployment to educated people and at the same time the existence of MGNREGS as a minimum wage provider for the population.

The economic times(2021) has reported that, it is very urgent to increase the working days of MGNREGS due to the decrease of casual working days and the ongoing reducing monthly income of common people. But the government is not willing to increase the working days. At the same time the central government has taken a loan of one billion dollar from National development bank to support the rural development and infrastructure development through NREGS which would be an aid for the unbalanced economy formed in pandemic. It also examine the critique of various scholars on the decline on the no.of applicants in the end of the year. Some suggest that it is due to the recovery of economy in the end of the year. But some suggested that it may be because of the slowing of work allocation of some states.

Sandeep singh (2021) in his article in NDTV report, strongly support the central government to grant an amount of 40000crore to Mahathmagandhi national rural employment guarantee schemes part of government's Athma nirbhar bharrath. He says that it will back up the economy which were crunched during the pandemic

In 'Implications of covid 19 on Gujarat on energy, emissions, climate and development perspective' the government has glorified the National rural employment guarantee scheme on its wage providing role in covid period. It points out to the condition of those people who were admitted in their own state as returned migrant workers. Actually the wage from MGNREGS is minimum when considering other daily casual workers. But it will help them to maintain their daily life.

Business standard (2021) reported about the special financial assistance provided by the Odisha government. The government provided an extra amount of 352 cores to the programme for the ongoing financial year. It will give an extra fifty rupees per day for each.

Rajalekshmi V (Journal of internet banking and commerce) says about women empowerment, issues and challenges of MGNREGS. She examines the improvement in condition of women which occurred due to the work. After getting the work social status which possessed by rural women were changed. Most of the rural women were spend their more time on kitchen and family matters. The deviation in their time spend was a big indicator of achieved empowerment and through this

Ajit ghose in "eSocial sciences" by "addressing the Employment Challenge: India's MGNREGA" examines the effect which occurred in work, wage and also on the economy of the country.

Sony pellisery in the article "Gender and development" by towards transformative social protection: a gendered analysis of the Employment Guarantee Act of India (MGNREGA)" discusses about the so called social transformation which where tried to implement through MGNREGS. The participation and the empowerment of women was established.

Susan lund in the article "Mckincey" by "The future of work after Covid 19" talk about the labor scenario occurred on the covid period. Covid was badly struck the labor market and lack of people were affected with it. He examines the situation of post pandemic on innovation and productivity.

BBC by "Coronavirus: How the world of work may change forever" discusses the threat on the longterm state of employment. Because the alternatives for unemployment are adapted within the period of one year. But it is not a permanent one. It examines the state of employment when every person may see in work from home or working online. By comparing with men, the rate of loss of job for women was high in rate at the beginning of pandemic. In some part of the society, women had to spend more time on unpaid works like child care, cleaning, etc. It became conflict when women have to focus on work especially online or work from home along with the above mentioned unpaid workers.

Praveen jha and Manishkumar (2019) in "Indian economic journal" says about the changes which occurred in indian employment sector. After the new approved economic policy in 1991, even the basic employment fields were affected at macro level. After the new economic policy,

Received: 22 July 2023

Revised: 2 August 2023

Final Accepted 8 August 2023

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8224098>

the working sector were predicted with more efficiency, energy, resource allocation, employment, inflation and foreign trade. But at the same time a noticeable change was occurred in the commodity producing sector. The sector on which India's economy was build changed to the service sector. It indirectly point out to the lean occurred in the lives of base line workers like farmers, casual workers, daily wage workers, etc. Decreasing commodity price and the increasing level of poverty and malnutrition among rural people were started to reaching it's peak from those time. The decreasing commodity prize and low income were discouraged the Indian youth from above mentioned works. The implementation of MGNREGS works changed the scenario of low income during the lean season.

Kang hyun park and A Ram kim (2021) in journal “Plos.org” by “Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the lifestyle, mental health, and quality of life of adults in South Korea” discusses the impact of covid pandemic on the social life of common people in south Korea. He has viewed the picture of social changes which formed on the daily life. The author has clearly notified about the change occurred in social interaction among people whether it is regarding common people or urban side.

Abid halim and Mohd javaid (2021) in “PMC” explained about the covid19 pandemic and how it impacted the life. COVID-19 has an impact on daily life and is slowing the global economy. This pandemic has affected thousands of people, who are either sick or dying as a result of the disease's spread. The most common symptoms of this viral infection are fever, cold, cough, bone pain, and breathing difficulties, which can progress to pneumonia. This is a new viral disease that has been affecting humans for the first time. Vaccines are not yet available for the first time. As a result, the emphasis is on taking precautions such as extensive hygiene protocol, social distancing, and mask wearing, among other things. This virus is rapidly spreading across the country. Countries are prohibiting mass gatherings of people in order to spread and break the exponential curve. It has impacted the industries, agriculture, daily works, and projects along with the huge financial crisis. The interruption in cash flow had affected the daily activities of government which included the financial assistance in social, health and economic sectors.

Dagmar Walter (2020) in “PMS” by “Implications of Covid-19 for Labor and Employment in India” have examined the impacts of corono virus in the country. He talk about the influence of virus not only on the health sector but in a large meaning it has badly affected the economic and labor market.

Clare wenham in "Nature" COVID-19 has a greater social and economic impact on women than on men. To keep all individuals safe, sheltered, and secure, governments must collect data and target policies. The social and economic consequences of infectious illness outbreaks harm women more than men. They bear the brunt of care obligations as schools close and family members fall ill and they are disproportionately affected by limited access to sexual- and reproductive-health services. Women are more affected by job losses in times of economic

uncertainty than men because they have fewer hours of paid labour and are more likely to be on insecure or zero-hour contracts. . Women's socioeconomic security was upended during the recent Ebola and Zika virus outbreaks², and for a longer period of time than men's¹. Quarantines shuttered marketplaces for food and other commodities during the West African Ebola outbreak in 2014–16, for example. Traders in Sierra Leone and Liberia, 85 percent of whom were women⁵, saw their livelihoods ruined as a result of this. At the same time, too little is known about how epidemics affect men and women differently. As a result, political and policy responses may be rendered ineffective. Only a small number of governments collect and exchange basic, gender-disaggregated data on infectious disease cases and the socio-economic consequences of outbreak responses. The analysis is still at a high level, frequently done after the fact and with incomplete data. Gaps must be filled this time.

Babagana mala masti and Ahmad mallum in “**Journal of business and economic development**” The effects of casual employment on the government's poverty alleviation initiatives and economic growth in Nigeria are examined in this article. The research looked at the existing literature on casual work and its effects on poverty in society and the economy. The questionnaire provided to sampled respondents was analyzed as part of the study, which used a survey method. The study discovered that casual employees' salary and working conditions are not comparable to those of permanent employees. Casual employees are frequently not paid the minimum wage, which is a monthly wage, because they are underemployed and hence do not receive the minimum wage. In our poll, we discovered that 59 percent of respondents earn less than the minimum wage on a monthly basis. It demonstrates that casual work is incompatible with government programmes aimed at increasing employment and reducing poverty. Casual work is harmful to employees and has serious ramifications for the firm and the national economy. In every organization, casual employees are generally low-level employees. They've been labelled as unskilled laborers by many. According to the survey, 26% of casual staff respondents received tertiary education, compared to 40% of full-time employees. In comparison, 35% of casual employees have no formal education, compared to 26% of full-time employees. The study indicates that casual labor, as it is practiced in Nigeria, is a threat to intended economic growth and a source of poverty. Employers can overlook workplace norms and workers' social requirements when they use the casual employment model. The trend in society toward casual employment is a sign of rising poverty. According to the report, the government should examine the casualization of work in the employment system, which has a significant negative influence on the economy.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

MGNREGS as a tool of financial security among people during pandemic covid19: a study in peringamala grama panchayath.

Introduction

Received: 22 July 2023

Revised: 2 August 2023

Final Accepted 8 August 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8224098>

About 3 crores of Indian population are depend on the NREGS work in India. By providing 100 working days people earns an income in between twenty thousand to thirty thousand. Most of them are women and the scheme has made the Indian women empowered and self-employed. The government is responsible for ensuring the working days.

Significance of the study

MGNREGS workers get job according to Mahatma Gandhi national rural employment guarantee act 2005. According to this act every worker registered as employee should get 100 working days in each year. It is not supposed to do a fixed quantity of work for every worker. It helped the rural unemployed people especially women to find out job and earnings in lean seasons. In the period of covid 19, like any other workers mgnregs workers were also lost job. But after three months they retained the working days. It is an interesting one to know about how it played as a security for their lives.

The study evaluated the acquired financial security of workers and it's effect on various aspects such as health, daily needs, etc. The study also aimed to understand the changes in social and economic condition of workers before and after the lockdown.

GENERAL OBJECTIVES

General objective of the study is to understand the mgnregs as a tool of financial security for people during covid pandemic period.

Specific objectives

1. To study about the social and financial status of the workers in the time of lock down
2. To study about the impact of covid 19 on the health aspect of workers
3. To examine the role of NREGS as a social security scheme during pandemic
4. To study about the financial and social empowerment that acquired by workers after getting the working days.

DEFINITION

Theoretical definition

MGNREGA

Mahatma Gandhi national rural employment guarantee act 2005 is an Indian labor law and a social security measure which aims to guarantee the working days.

MGNREGS

Mahatma Gandhi national rural employment guarantee scheme is a scheme working according to MGNREGA.

It aims to enhance livelihood security by providing 100 days of wage employment in a financial year to every adult members of a family who are volunteer to do unskilled manual work.

TOOL

A tool is an instrument that you use to help you accomplish some task.

FINANCIAL SECURITY

Financial security means having enough money to fund your life style, as well as work towards your financial goal.

COVID 19

Corona virus disease is an infectious disease which caused by corona virus.

PANDEMIC

Pandemic is the outbreak of an infectious disease which occurs over a wide geographical area and that is of high prevalence, generally affecting a significant population of the world.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITION

MGNREGA

The act which was enacted in the year of 2005 to provide unemployed population with wage employment

MGNREGS

The scheme which working according to Mahatma Gandhi national rural employment guarantee act to enhance people with livelihood by providing 100 days of unskilled manual work.

TOOL

A tool is any instrument which can be used to achieve any particular task

FINANCIAL SECURITY

It is a state of financial empowerment to do own life task without any financial difficulties

COVID 19

Covid 19 is the corona virus disease which caused by corona virus all over the world which announced as a pandemic in last year

PANDEMIC

Pandemic is the condition of an epidemic when it strikes over the boundaries.

RESEARCH DESIGN

Considering the nature of the study and to accomplish the objectives, the researcher

Adopted a descriptive research design for the study. Descriptive research design involves

Collecting data in order to answer questions concerning the current status of the subject of the

Study. In this study descriptive research design is used to understand the mgnregs as a tool of financial security among people during covid 19 in peringamala panchayath of Thiruvananthapuram district. The study experience Quantitative Research. The Quantitative Research is the form of

Interview schedule conducted with the help of structured Questionnaire and sample selected from 100 mgnregs workers from peringamala gramapanchayath

PILOT STUDY

Pilot study undertaken by the researcher to identify the feasibility, cost, data collection method and

research tool of the study. A pilot study was conducted for the respective research topic at peringamala grama panchayath.

UNIVERSE OF THE STUDY

The researcher decided to conduct study among MGNREGS workers in peringamala gramapanchayath of Thiruvananthapuram district, Kerala state in India. 4120 active workers are there in peringamala grama panchayath

UNIT OF THE STUDY

The researcher conducted study among 100 MGNREGS workers in peringamala gramapanchayath.

VARIABLES

The variables used in the study are Age, Educational qualification, Income, Marital status, experience, motivating factor.

SOURCE OF DATA

1. Primary source of data

Primary source of data which is collected directly from the respondents (mgnregs workers in peringamala gramapanchayath) by the researcher. The researcher collected data from 100 respondents

2. Secondary source of data

Researcher collected secondary source of data from previous research records, Articles, PDFs, magazines, net sources etc.

SAMPLING METHOD

Sample selection is very important step in any research study, sampling is the process of selecting a subset of the population in which the entire population is represented. From the different sampling techniques, purposive sampling (non probability sampling method) was selected by the researcher for the particular research study. The researcher has selected 100 respondents from the peringamala panchayath

TOOLS FOR DATA COLLECTION

The tool used for the data collection is the interview schedule. The questions related to different economic challenges, changes in social interaction due to covid 19, working days, expenditure,

social, challenges occurred in lockdown are included in the questionnaire. There are 34 questions in the questionnaire.

METHOD OF ANALYSIS

PRE TEST

Pretest is conducted by the researcher among five respondents to verify whether the questionnaire is matching with the objectives of the study. This will help the researcher to restructure the questionnaire if it is needed.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. The research study is conducting with in a limited time duration
2. The workers are busy with their daily work
3. Covid conditions restricts the travel
4. All the area are not covering due to the time limitations and restrictions.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

This chapter deals with the analysis and interpretation of collected quantitative data. The quantitative data is analyzed on the basis of objectives and presented here. The data are collected in a master sheet and analyzed in the basis of objectives by applying appropriate methods such as computation of frequencies and percentage.

Table 4.1

Age wise distribution

AGE	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
18-25	0	0
26-40	12	12
41-60	69	69
Above 60	19	19

Among the selected population more than 50% of people have the age group 41-60

Table 4.2

Sex

Sex	No . of respondent	percentage
Male	6	6
Female	94	94
Other	0	0

94% of population are women. This shows the large participation of women in MGNREGS

Table 4.3

Educational qualification

Education	No . of respondent	Percentage
Below 8	38	38
9-10	41	41
HSE	20	20
Above HSE	1	1
other	0	0

About 40% people have studied in 9-10 and 38% people have educational qualification below 8. only one person have HSE qualification.

Table 4.4

Marital status

Marital status	No . of respondent	Percentage
Married	100	100
Unmarried	0	0

All the workers are married. Only married people are willing to do the job.

Table 4.5

Monthly income

Income	No . of respondent	Percentage
Below5000	9	9
5000-10000	45	45
10000-20000	42	42
20000-50000	4	4
Above 50000	0	0

45% peoples have the family income in between 5000-10000 and 42% peoples include in the range of 10000-20000.

Table 4.6

Experience as a MGNREGS worker

Experience	No . of respondent	Percentage
0-1	0	0
1-5	11	11
5-10	44	44
Above 10	45	45

Almost equal number of people shares the working experience of 5-10 and above 10.

Table 4.7

Getting 100 working days in each year

100 working days	No . of respondent	Percentage
Yes	23	23
No	77	77

Only 77% people got 100 days of working days after restart of MGNREGS work.

Table 4.8

Motivating factor

Motivating factor	No . of respondent	Percentage
Income	94	94
Time pass	4	4
Interest	2	2
To improve social contact	0	0

94% people are motivated by the income factor for joining the work.

Table 4.9

Percentage of

MGNREGS as main source of income

MGNREGS as main source of income	No . of respondent	Percentage
Yes	41	41
No	59	59

59% people have the MGNREGS income as the main source. This shows it's importance in their daily life.

Table 4.10

Main monthly income usage of family

Need	No . of respondent	Percentage
Food	81	81
Health	3	3
Education	1	1
Rent	2	2
Loan	13	13

81% of people uses the monthly income mainly for food. 3% for health and 2% for rent. Only

1% use the monthly income mainly for education.

Table 4.11

Main usage of MGNREGS income

Need	No . of respondent	Percentage
Food	73	73
Health	9	9
Education	2	2
Rent	2	2
Loan	14	14

73% of people use the main source of MGNREGS fund for food. 9% use the main source for health. And 2% shares it for education and loan.

Table 4.12**No of families whose requirements satisfied within the income**

Respond	No . of respondent	Percentage
Yes	59	59
No	41	41

About 59% people are satisfied within their income.

Table 4.13**Situation of no income during lock down**

Respond	No . of respondent	Percentage
Yes	71	71
No	29	29

71% people faced no income situation during lockdown.

Table 4.14

Any bad impacts during lock down Due to income reduction

Need	No . of respondent	Percentage
Food	69	69
Health	53	53
Education	24	24
Rent	5	5
Loan	43	43
Nil	10	10

69% people faced bad impacts of covid for food. 53% people face it in health. 24% people faced the same for education. 43% people faced the bad impact for paying loan. Only 5% people faced difficulty in paying rent. At the same time 10% people face any bad impacts during lockdown for any of the mentioned.

Table 4.15

Faced isolation during lockdown

Respond	No . of respondent	Percentage
Yes	9	9
No	91	91

About 91% people never faced the condition of isolation in family due to no income situation.

Table 4.16

The change occurred in social interaction at the time of lockdown

Social interaction	No . of respondent	Percentage
More increased	0	0
Increased	0	0
No change	10	10
Decreased	45	45
More decreased	45	45

45% of people shared the feeling of decreased and more decreased social interaction during lockdown. 10% people had no change in social interaction.

Table 4.17

Whether health expenditure increased in lockdown

Respond	No . of respondent	Percentage
Yes	45	45
No	55	55

Health expenditure of 45%of people were increased during lockdown.

Table 4.18

New diseases were reported during lockdown

Respond	No . of respondent	Percentage
Yes	22	22
No	78	78

Families of about 78% of people were reported with new diseases during lockdown.

Table 4.19

Whether family faced covid related treatment

Respond	No . of respondent	Percentage
Yes	18	18
No	82	82

Only families of 18% people were faced covid related treatment. 82% people were able to avoid covid crisis.

Table 4.20

Worker rejoined when MGNREGS restarted after lock down

Respond	No . of respondent	Percentage
Yes	100	100
No	0	0

All the selected population rejoined the work after restart of MGNREGS.

Table4.21

Days of working after restart of work

Days	No . of respondent	Percentage
0-30	0	0
30-60	25	25
60-90	62	62
90-120	13	13
120-150	0	0
150-200	0	0

About 62% of people worked 60-90 days after the restart of working days. 25% people worked for 30-60 days and 13% of people worked more than 90 days.

Table 4.22

Getting income periodically after lockdown

Respond	No . of respondent	Percentage
Yes	100	100
No	0	0

All the selected workers got income periodically after the restart of working days.

Table 4.23

Main usage of income after restart of work

Need	No . of respondent	Percentage
Food	73	73
Health	11	11
Education	0	0
Rent	2	2
Loan	14	14
All	0	0

73% of people used the large portion of MGNREGS income for food. 14% of people used the main portion for loan and 11% of workers used the main portion for health. Only 2% used the main portion for rent and no people used the main portion of income for education.

Table 4.24

Facing difficulties to met basic needs even after getting working days

Respond	No . of respondent	Percentage
More difficulty	0	0
Less difficulty	4	4
No change	7	7
Slightly easy	68	68
More easy	21	21

Almost 90% of people is feeling easy in meet basic needs after getting MGNREGS working days. But 4% of population faced less difficulty in meeting basic needs even after the restart of working days.

Table 4.25

Social interaction after getting working days

Social interaction	No. of respondent	Percentage
More increased	83	83
increased	14	14
No change	3	3
Decreased	0	0
More decreased	0	0

Social interaction of 897% of people were increased after the restart of working days. Only 3%of people faced no change in social interaction even after the restart of working days.

Table 4.26

Whether free to use the income from MGNREGS

Degree of freedom	No . of respondent	Percentage
Free to use	78	78
With concern of partner	14	14
Not free to use	8	8
No interest	0	0

78% of people are free to use the income from MGNREGS for their own need. 14% of people can use their income for their own need with concern of partner. But 8% of people are not free to use their income.

Table 4.27

Whether able to use the income for extra expenditure in the family

Respond	No . of respondent	Percentage
Most likely	24	24
Often	21	21
Some time	41	41
Never	15	15

41% of population are able to use their income for their extra expenditure for some times. Most likely 24% of people are able to use the income for extra expenditure. 21% of population are able to do the same

often. And 15% of population are never able to use the income for extra expenditure.

FINDINGS

- More than 50% of MGNREGS workers are in the age group of 41-60
- 94% of workers are women
- Most of their educational qualification range from 9-10
- All of the workers are married
- Most of the workers have monthly income in the range of 5000-10000
- Most of them are MGNREGS workers being for more than 10 years.
- Only 23% of them have get 100 days of work
- Income is the motivating factor for most of the workers.
- Nearly 50% of workers have income from MGNREGS as main source.
- Most of them are using the large portion of annual and MGNREGS income for food.
- More than half of the population are satisfying their requirements with the income
- Most of the family faced no income situation in lockdown period
- Most of the people had bad impacts in food, health and paying loan
- Health expenditure of nearly half of the population was increased during the time of lockdown.
- Nearly 80% of the people were responded that, their family was not hitted by any new diseases.
- Covid19 disease was reported only among 20% of the population.
- All of the workers were able to rejoin the work after restart of MGNREGS after lockdown.

- Most of these workers were able to meet 60-90 working days.
- All of the workers get income periodically
- After getting the working days, the income was used for food by most of the workers.
- Most of the workers experienced some sort of relief in satisfying the basic needs after getting the income
- A large population are independent to use their own income from MGNREGS for their own interest.
- For the rural population it is not possible to use the income for for extra expenditure for all time. But a 40% population are able to use it for some times.

SUGGESIONS

- The wage per day of a worker should increase from 294 to 350
- The government should implement financial schemes for the workers to compensate the covid crisis.
- There should be create provision for individual works for workers who are willing to do the job at the time of such crisis.
- By considering the age and the labor which spend for work, special health services for MGNREGS workes should be create in panchayath level like emergency transportation to hospital, home delivery of medicines and weekend checkups by health professionals
- The service of tele counselling should be given to the workers because, most of them become house wives from the stage of daily worker. It may impact their psychological level badly.
- Give training to manage the psychological level and maintain the stress.
- The local body should provide special consideration towards the education of MGNREGS worker's children

CONCLUSION

The Mahatma Gandhi national rural employment guarantee scheme workers under MGNREG act has ensured with 100 unskilled manual working days by the local body. It was employed as a better tool against poverty and unemployment and it is efficiently working to accomplish the aim. Majority of the MGNREGS workers are women, so that the self-sufficiency and empowerment of Indian women are meted who were underprivileged condition. All of the workers are working for more than 5 hours and it can be affect their health. It cannot be avoided when considering the average age belongs to more than 50. The government should focus on the special health assistance for the workers. Like all other sectors MGNREGS workers were also faced issues. But it should be consider about their psychosocial and economic bad condition on that time. I realized that most workers faced health issues during lockdown and the social condition badly impacted their physical and psychological status. All of them are aware about their rights especially about the 100 days of work. But most of them are not able to fulfill it. Despite of leading simple life, their expected and unexpected expenditure are not in control. MGNREGS is the most depended thing when they face any financial crisis. And a social position created by MGNREGS especially for women are deserve a great appreciation. In such a scenario the wage should be increased and it is not asked by them so for long. The local body should concentrate on strengthening their mental health and also about the must needed social empowerment which they have gain through their involvement.

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